

Examining the Influence of Electoral Gifts, Political Debates, Social Media Political Activism, and Patriotism on Voters' Behavior

Lapologang Sebaka^{1*}, Bame Romeo Gaonyadiwe¹, Sherifath Chinaza Tahirou², Miapéh Kous Gonlepa³, Goabamang Lethugile⁴

¹ School of Public Affairs, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China

¹ Institute of Governance, Humanities and Social Sciences, Pan African University, Yaoundé, Cameroon

² School of Public Affairs, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China

³ School of Public Affairs, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China

⁴ African Centre for Cities, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa

Accepted November 23, 2021
Published November 27, 2021

*Corresponding Author:
Lapologang Sebaka
Sbk20@mail.ustc.edu.cn

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5730406>

Pages: 166-182

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Sebaka, L., Gaonyadiwe, B. M., Tahirou, S. C., Gonlepa, M & Lethugile, G. (2021). Examining the Influence of Electoral Gifts, Political Debates, Social Media Political Activism, and Patriotism on Voters' Behavior. *North American Academic Research*, 4(11), 166-182. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5730406>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The political landscape of Botswana has become more competitive and unpredictable in recent years. Elections are central to the functioning of any democratic nation. Given the turbulent political environment surrounding the 2019 General Elections, the factors influencing voters' behavior have aroused controversy. Bearing this in mind, the purpose of this study is to investigate the salience of electoral gifts, political debates, patriotism, and social media political activism as determinants of voters' behavior using the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). A questionnaire was used to collect data from 640 individuals who participated in the 2019 General Elections. The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique was used to analyze data. The study discovered that electoral gifts from political candidates significantly impacted voters' intent and attitude toward voting. Additionally, our study found that patriotism influenced voters' attitudes and intention to vote in the 2019 General Elections despite the tumultuous political environment. The study further confirmed the relevance of social media political activism on voters' intent and attitudes towards voting. The study also corroborated the influence of political debates on voters' behavior. The implications of this study and future research directions are further discussed in light of these findings.

Keywords: VOTERS' BEHAVIOR, PATRIOTISM, SOCIAL MEDIA POLITICAL ACTIVISM, ELECTORAL GIFTS, POLITICAL DEBATES, BOTSWANA

1 Introduction

The smooth transition of power in Botswana since the 1965 pre-independence elections has piqued the interest of international scholars on

Botswana Democracy. The smooth transition of power in Botswana since the 1965 pre-independence elections has piqued the interest of international scholars on Botswana Democracy. In Sub-Saharan Africa, Botswana is revered as a haven for peace and the epitome of democracy. The political landscape of Botswana has gradually changed. The appearance of stasis, however, the 2019 general elections belie what was undoubtedly the most competitive and unpredictable election in Botswana's history. Significant gains by the Umbrella Democratic Change (UDC) in the country's north were offset by significant Botswana Democratic Party (BDP) gains in the south. Perhaps the most dramatic aspect of the election, however, was the unprecedented intervention by former Botswana Democratic Party President Ian Khama, who defected from the party he had led for ten years to found a new party, the Botswana Patriotic Front (BPF), whose sole declared purpose was to remove the BDP from power. Considering the competitive political landscape during the 2019 General Elections, it is interesting to study voters' behavior to have a comprehensive understanding of voters' behavior. Further, the constitution arrangements bestow citizens the right to exercise their constitutional privileges and vote. Although the constitution establishes the framework for voting, the decision to vote is entirely up to the individual. Scholars who study voting behavior generally agree that certain social, psychological, and cultural factors influence people's voting intentions (Anderson, 2007; Harder & Krosnick, 2008). Given this backdrop, analyzing these factors will be beneficial to political parties to ensure the continuity of democracy.

Despite elections playing a critical role in Botswana's peaceful transition of power, little is known about the factors influencing voter behavior. In the context of voter behavior in emerging democratic societies, whereas Downs (1957) bases behavior on ideological, policy, and philosophical pillars, Bates (1974) and Young (2002) document lifelong attachment to political parties and candidates, social background and psychology, as well as political party track records. (Young, 2002) examines the ethnicity influence on voter behavior in apparent agreement with what Horowitz (1985) refers to as "political tribalism" and "ethnic censuses." However, most studies evaluating voters' behavior are based in Europe, American, Asia, and the Middle East context. Given that voter behavior is influenced by specific socio-cultural factors, we believe that voter behavior may differ from one geographical context to the next. As a result, applying a "one-size-fits-all" approach to assess voter behavior in Botswana based on the results of the other contests will be inappropriate.

Thus, it is critical to conduct a focused study to address Botswana's dearth of research on the antecedents of voter behavior. Drawing inspiration from studies conducted in other Sub-Saharan African countries, scholars have probed some antecedents of voters' intention. For example, a recent study by Arkorful & Lugu (2021) shed light on the impact of debates, manifestos, ideology, and celebrity endorsement on voter behavior in Ghana. Similarly, Kimenyi & Romero (2008), projected the significance of identity and economic determinants on Kenyan voters. Taken together these viewpoints, scholars Adams & Agomor, (2015); Bratton & Kimenyi, (2008); Dewa, (2009) underscored the role of ethnicity on voters' decision-making process in Sub-Saharan Africa. Given the highlighted dynamism and sophistication of voters' behavior, and more profoundly, the competitive environment in which elections are held, it becomes critical for political parties in Botswana to

understand voters' decision-making factors. As such, our study's proximate motivation borders on investigating voters' behavior in Botswana. With reference to the 2019 General Election, we examine the collective importance of political debates, social media political activism, electoral gifts, and patriotism in Botswana and establish their collective influence on voters' voting intention behavior using Structural Equation Modelling. On this basis, we propose a conceptual framework for research grounded in the theory of reasoned action.

To the authors' knowledge, there are few quantitative studies in Botswana that examine voter behavior variables. This study makes several contributions to African politics literature. To begin, this study will advance understanding of the underlying motivations of voters in countries aspiring to be democratic beyond Botswana. It is critical for public organizations such as political parties to be aware of these. Second, the formulation of a theoretical framework and validation of its predictive potential, as well as the associated hypotheses, will be significant for not only the deployment and decision-making of political parties' strategic strategies but also for their understanding of civic behavior (i.e., participation in voting) performance correlates. Thirdly, our findings will advance knowledge and contribute to the academic debates on politics and democracy literature.

The remainder of this paper is divided into the following sections: Section 2 discusses the theoretical background and hypotheses development. The methodology is discussed in Section 3. Section 4 highlights the data analysis and results. Section 5 presents a discussion of findings. The concluding section discusses the limitations and future research directions.

2 Theoretical Background and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Theoretical Foundation of the study

Ajzen & Fishbein (1975) proposed the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which includes normative, attitude-based, and behavior-prediction variables like intention. As a behavioral paradigm, the theory asserts that the key determinant of behavior is intention (comprised of a functional set of information or belief). To classify the beliefs that underlie behavior and the normative elements of a belief system, Ajzen & Fishbein (1975), used a conceptual framework. Contrary to behavioral beliefs, normative aspects reinforce individual behavior performance via subjective norms. As a result, attitudes and subjective norms are influenced by the integration of information and beliefs, which in turn affects intention behavior performance. External variables may have an impact on the formation of intentions and subsequent behavior performance, even though beliefs and information play a significant role (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975). There is evidence that the ability of an individual to exert voluntary control over their actions is connected to their behavioral outcomes (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975). Previous electoral studies have shown that TRA can accurately predict the outcome of an election (Arkorful & Lugu, 2021; Mohanachandran & Govindarajo, 2020). The model depicted in Fig. 1 is based on the preceding discourse and replicates the TRA in our study context to investigate voting intention.

According to our model, voting intention behavior is mediated by attitude, which is determined by the additive contribution of subjective variables such as patriotism, electoral gifts, social media political activism, and political debates. Voting intention is determined by taking into account the contributions of all of these variables, both additive and incremental (i.e., patriotism, electoral gifts, social media political activism, and political debates).

2.2 Empirical Setting of the Study

Botswana's most recent elections were on 23 October 2019; it marked the 12th democratic general elections for the parliamentary and local government since independence. Botswana has used the First Past the Post (FPTP) electoral system since independence, and elections are conducted within the framework of multiparty democracy and parliamentary system. This means that until today, only Members of Parliament can be elected by the electorates and in succession elect the president. All these processes transpire within the guidance of the 1966 Constitution of Botswana and the 1968 Electoral Act (Datta, 1991). Despite the country's good record of peaceful, free, and fair democratic elections, the Botswana Democratic Party (BDP) has controlled and kept state power since independence, making it a one-party state. The Botswana Independent Electoral Commission (IEC) supervises the general elections in response to complaints about the Permanent Secretary's autonomy in handling the elections initially. Following such complaints, the office of Supervisor of Elections was established, albeit its autonomy was questioned because the Supervisor was also appointed by the President. This resulted in the foundation of the Botswana Independent Electoral Commission in 1999, which oversaw that year's elections, decreased the voting age from 21 to 18, and allowed nationals living overseas to vote.

2.3 Hypotheses Development

2.3.1 Social Media Activists-Attitude-Intention

People primarily use social media to access political content to satiate their political curiosity and increase their political knowledge, as well as to connect with various political pundits as members of a real-time virtual political community (Steinberg, 2015). This virtual community is referred to as SM activists, which refers to political commentators who engage in online political participation within the social media space. They engage in political and ideological debate, legislative deliberation, and possibly even persuasion. As a result of these connections, individuals form a variety of political groups (Bimber, 1998). They collaborate through the exchange of political information (views, opinions), much like they do outside of social media space. There are numerous advantages to this, including members of these collaborations developing long-term relationships with political pundits, politicians, commentators, and presidential candidates Tang and Lee (2013). Its advantage is that it enables political discussion (and spontaneous conversation) across the platform's various dimensions via tweets, chats, and videos, with tens of thousands of people concurrently (Bimber, 1998). Political activism on social media has exploded in popularity; almost all political parties now have a presence on the platform, and independent scholars use it to spread the word about the importance of voting. When

people learn about the benefits of voting through social media, they are more likely to do so because of their newfound knowledge and information.

Masilo & Seabo (2015) claim that Botswana's elections have undergone a major shift, particularly in 2014 highly contested election. Social media, particularly Facebook, has provided a platform for opposition parties, in particular, to gain fair and inexpensive access to the media. High voter mobilization was achieved through the use of social media, and traditional media outlets began to use social media as a means of expanding their reach. Facebook improved access to timely and unfiltered information from candidates and activists, and as a result, many Facebook users were ecstatic because of the easy access to political debates and discussion of issues at the time. Guardado and Wantchekon, (2017) found that more than a third of Botswana have access to news via Facebook, Twitter, or any other social media platform and that most believe social media is important in helping them become better informed and better citizens. 73% of those who have heard of social media state that it assists them in making informed decisions about current events (91%), and is also critical in assisting them in becoming more active in political processes. Given the above background, we propose that social media activism plays a crucial role in influencing voters' attitudes and intentions towards voting.

H1: Social media political activism has a significant positive with voting intention.

H2: Social media political activism has a significant positive relationship with attitude.

2.3.2 Patriotism-Attitude

Results from Richey (2011) study on patriotism and civic participation revealed a strong connection between patriotism and civic participation, such as voting as an example of civic participation. Patriotism is a term that refers to an individual's "degree of attachment to and pride in his or her country" (Kosterman & Feshbach, 1989). To help better understand patriotism, Schatz et al. (1999) classify it into two types: blind patriotism and constructive patriotism. Blind patriotism is also known as uncritical patriotism, as it is characterized by a reluctance to criticize and also by a reluctance to embrace criticism of one's nation, regardless of whether the criticism is justified or not. It is a strong attachment and affection for one's country regardless of the circumstances, unwavering devotion to one's country. The other side of patriotism is constructive, in which critical loyalty refers to a person's devotion to his or her country; the central concept of constructive patriotism is to accept responsibility for what occurs in a country. The reason for this is so that they can be a positive change or improvement (Milotova, 2021). Richey (2011) argued that civic participation is boosted by constructive patriotism, whereas blind patriotism is detrimental.

Patriotism has become an integral part of the political landscape culture in both developed and developing countries, such as the United States of America and Botswana. Patriotism is an umbrella term that encompasses values such as commitment and loyalty. These principles vary according to an individual's subjective view of the country. We believe that patriotism is likely to influence an individual's voting attitude. For instance, an individual who is patriotic about his country may have a more favorable attitude toward voting than an

unpatriotic individual. [Schatz et al., \(1999\)](#) found that Americans with a strong sense of patriotism were more aware of and engaged in political issues, with a higher likelihood of voting. They demonstrate a strong relationship between constructive patriotism and political engagement. [Milotová, \(2009\)](#) supports the preceding statement by arguing that the more patriotic an individual is, the more likely he or she is to participate in political issues. We hypothesize that patriotism is likely to influence an individual's attitude towards voting.

H3: Patriotism has a positive significant relationship with attitude towards voting.

2.3.3 Electoral Gifts-Attitude

It is customary to exchange goods such as cash and gifts for electoral support or a high level of attendance and participation on election day. This is a common occurrence in developing democracies, and electoral gift giving has the ability to completely alter an individual's political behavior compared to when such gifts were not given. Additionally, this factor cannot be used to predict election results because it comes from a variety of politicians and political parties; it is merely a way to demonstrate that a particular candidate is in electoral competition and vying for votes ([Guardado & Wantchekon, 2021](#)). It is common for politicians in Botswana's competitive political landscape to give away gifts during political campaigns in order to entice voters. The impact of electoral gifts is felt most acutely in less privileged communities, influencing their behavior towards voting. According to an Afrobarometer study, Botswana, Uganda, Kenya, and Mali all had a high positive and statistically significant coefficient, indicating that electoral gifts were most likely to influence voting behavior in these countries ([Guardado and Wantchekon, 2014](#)). Furthermore, [Nichter \(2008\)](#) argued in related studies that parties do not attempt to buy votes but rather to increase turnout, a strategy that circumvents commitment issues. Electoral gifts may improve voter engagement.

H4: Electoral gifts have a significant positive relationship attitude

2.3.4 Political Debates-Attitude-Intention

In many democracies, political debates are now viewed as critical components of campaign outreach. In multi-party electoral countries such as Botswana, debates allow incumbents and challengers to speak for themselves. Debates can elicit information about candidates' policy positions, qualifications and competence, and personalities, potentially swaying an individual's voting decision. Along with allowing candidates to converse with one another about policy issues, debate assists in the synthesis and articulation of information necessary for effective decision making in situations where a candidate or candidates have limited access to information ([Brierley et al., 2020](#)). Voters are more likely to vote for a candidate or party they favor when they have a positive attitude toward the candidates' policy proposals and are more likely to appreciate candidates who offer realistic and achievable policy alternatives.

In a study conducted in Sierra Leone during the 2012 Parliamentary elections, [Bidwell et al., \(2016\)](#), discovered that electoral campaigns distribute information about the candidate and their policies. Political

debates increased voter awareness of, among other things, candidates' educational backgrounds and policy positions, and as a result, voters with similar policy preferences aligned themselves with candidates who shared those positions. In general, voters became more receptive to candidates from different political parties, and the critical point is that the knowledge gained resulted in changes in votes cast; candidates who performed well during debates saw an average increase of five percentage points in vote shares. Additionally, when historical connections between political parties and ethnic groups were analyzed, a shift occurred as candidates who performed well in debates received votes from both rival ethnic groups and loyalists; all of these instances indicate a high level of voter responsiveness to information accessed during political debates. Using this logic, we infer that debates are likely to generate good attitudes and voting intentions.

H5: Political debates have a significant positive relationship with attitude

H6: Political debates have a significant positive relationship with the intention to vote.

2.3.5 Attitude- Voting Intention

Attitude toward a specific assignment, object, or task can be described as one's evaluation of the situation (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1977). People's attitude is an indicator of how they feel about their own behavior, according to (Arkorful et al., 2020). We define a voter's attitude toward a candidate or political party in terms of whether they like or dislike them. When it comes to political parties and candidates, an individual's attitude is what determines how much they like or dislike them. To put it another way, a positive voter behavior performance is influenced by one's attitude. A positive and favorable attitude toward a candidate or political party's viability is associated with a greater tendency or inclination toward acting out that attitude. Therefore, the following hypothesis is a possibility.

H7: Attitude has a significant positive relationship with voting intention.

The following page presents the proposed conceptual model. **Fig 1**

Figure 1. Proposed Conceptual Model

3 Methodology

3.1 Study Design

The study population consisted of Botswana voters. Their inclusion was justified based on their voting participation. As a result, voters were randomly selected from across Botswana's polling stations using purposive sampling. Individuals who voted in the general elections on 23rd October 2019 were eligible to participate. The study was quantitative – one section was devoted to the technique of structural equation modeling. This strategy was chosen in light of the study's objective of validating the proposed research model while establishing construct correlations (**Fig. 1**). The data collection instrument was a self-administered questionnaire. Prior to administering the questionnaire, participants were informed of the study's purpose and their consent was confirmed. Three research assistants were engaged to assist with data collection. Prior to the actual data collection, these assistants received a one-week training session. 750 questionnaires were distributed; 110 questionnaires were deemed invalid. The study then used 640 valid questionnaires to analyze the data. Representing a response rate of 85 percent. **Table 1** presents the demographics of study objects.

3.2 Measurement Scales

The constructs and their respective measurements used in the study were assessed using multiple scale items adapted from prior studies that had been tried, tested, and proven to be reliable and valid. The measurements were fine-tuned to fit the context of the study. Precisely, 5 measurement items for patriotism were adapted from (Theiss-Morse et al., 1991). These items were fine-tuned to fit the context of this study. Attitude-related items were adapted from (Arkorful et al., 2020). Furthermore, items for debate were adapted from (Brierley et al., 2020). Electoral gift was measured using items adapted from (Castro Cornejo and Beltrán, 2020). Finally, items for “intention” were adapted from (Arkorful and Lugu, 2021). To measure social media political activism we used items from (Frimpong et al., 2020). These study items were rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from

strongly disagree to strongly agree. The four-point Likert scale was chosen over the seven-point Likert scale because it facilitates a more nuanced understanding of construct relationships.

Table 1 Demographics

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
<i>Male</i>	404	63.1
<i>Female</i>	236	36.9
Age		
<i>18-20</i>	20	3.1
<i>21-30</i>	140	21.9
<i>31-40</i>	200	31.3
<i>41-50</i>	204	31.9
<i>Above 50</i>	76	11.9
Occupation		
<i>Tertiary student</i>	24	3.8
<i>Public sector employee</i>	424	66.3
<i>Commercial entrepreneurship</i>	4	.6
<i>Private Sector Employee</i>	116	18.1
<i>Self-employed</i>	48	7.5
Education Level		
<i>Doctorates</i>	131	20.5
<i>Masters</i>	169	26.4
<i>Degree</i>	132	20.6
<i>Diploma</i>	175	27.3
<i>High School Certificate</i>	33	5.2
Total	640	100.0

4 Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Data Analysis

Due to the quantitative nature of the study and the requirement to establish relationships between study constructs, the structural equation modeling (SEM) technique was used. The SEM technique was chosen due to its versatility (a) ability to evaluate a series of direct and indirect relationships in a model at the same time; (b) strength to examine latent and observed variables relationships; (c) capacity to validate variables using a cluster of indicators and test hypotheses at construct levels; (d) effectiveness to provide precise measurements by modeling random errors in observed variables (Arkorf and Lugu, 2021; Hair et al., 2013). SEM analysis was used to evaluate hypotheses. The Analysis of Moments of Structures (AMOS) software version 24.0 and the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 26.0 were used to analyze the data. The two-step SEM technique was used in this instance (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). This step includes estimations of the measurement model's basic parameters, which are used to test construct correlations, verify construct reliability and validity, and estimate the structural model's parameters. Correlations between latent variables and their associated measurement items were tested using the measurement model. On the other hand, the structural model was used to test and verify latent variables. Correlations between latent variables and their associated

measurement items were tested using the measurement model. On the other hand, the structural model was used to test and verify latent variables.

4.2 Result Analysis

Table 2 presents the sampling adequacy results. KMO is a test conducted to examine the strength of the partial correlation (how the factors explain each other) between the variables. Values above 0.5 are normally accepted for factor analysis (Kaiser, 1974). Our KMO result is .721 which is **acceptable**.

Table 2 Sampling Adequacy

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.721
Bartlett's	Approx. Chi-Square	1414.515
Test of		
Sphericity	Df	153
	Sig.	.000

We used Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to determine the values of factor loadings greater than 0.7. As illustrated in Table 4, loadings exceeded the recommended threshold (Hair et al., 2010). Cronbach alpha and composite reliability were used to assess the reliability of constructs. The values greater than 0.70 are confirmed by Table 5 (Hair et al., 2010). To assess the validity of the measurement model, firstly, we looked at the average variance extracted (AVE), also known as convergent validity. The AVE values (Table 5) exceed 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010). The AVE values range from 0.98 to 0.65, indicating that our items account for at least half of the variance in their respective constructs.

Table 3 Fornell-Lacker Discriminant Validity

	ATT	INT	SMP	PATR	ELG	DEB
ATT	.815					
INT	.162*	.842				
SMP	.316**	.159*	.989			
PATR	.475**	.101	.315**	.884		
ELG	.268**	.189*	.142	.113	.856	
DEB	.134**	.310**	.069	.051	.263**	.848

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Secondly, we looked at the measurement model's discriminant validity at the item and construct levels. Cross-loadings were lower at the item level than their corresponding factor loads (Henseler et al., 2015). At the construct level, scores of discriminant validity using AVE revealed sufficient thresholds. As a result, it indicates that the AVE square root value is greater than the correlations between the constructs, providing sufficient evidence of validity. Table 3 presents discriminant validity at the construct level.

Table 4 Factor Loadings and Cross Loadings

Construct	Items	SMP	PTR	ELG	BEB	INT	ATT
Social Media Political Activism	SMP1	.907	-.038	-.018	.073	-.031	-.012
	SMP2	.980	.001	-.024	-.093	.036	-.062
	SMP3	.859	.014	.029	.074	.018	.101
Patriotism	PTR1	-.066	.818	-.102	-.039	.081	.006
	PTR2	.011	.927	.105	.050	-.064	.023
	PTR3	.026	.906	-.018	.015	-.028	.039
Election Gifts	ELG1	-.033	.049	.875	-.054	.125	.016
	ELG2	.095	-.058	.853	-.007	-.076	-.055
	ELG3	-.084	.006	.841	.043	-.029	.022
Debates	DEB1	.010	-.143	.051	.716	-.041	.181
	DEB2	-.007	.081	-.064	.919	.008	-.060
	DEB3	.024	.047	.016	.896	.046	-.086
Intention	INT1	.085	-.063	-.007	-.043	.840	.020
	INT2	-.089	-.102	-.011	.049	.857	.139
	INT3	.033	.150	.030	.024	.831	-.150
Attitude	ATT1	-.076	-.021	-.046	-.013	.052	.834
	ATT2	.147	.117	.015	-.109	-.014	.809
	ATT3	-.046	-.010	.018	.087	-.031	.803

4.2.1 Structural Model Results Analysis

Typically, model fit is classified into three categories: absolute fit, incremental fit, and parsimonious fit. We used a variety of indices to assess the model's goodness, including degree of freedom (df), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Incremental Fit Index (NIF), Turker-Lewis Index, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). This study demonstrated in Table 6 that the best analytic practical measures of good fitness are the RMSEA, CFI, and TLI (Lewis, 2017). Other indices GFI, AGFI, IFI, and CMIN/DF also met the standard threshold, consistent with (Arkorful and Lugu, 2021).

Table 5 CR, AVE, and CA

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	CR	AVE	CA
Social Media Political Activism	SMP1	0.907	0.94	0.98	0.922
	SMP2	0.98			
	SMP3	0.859			
Patriotism	PTR1	0.818	0.915	0.783	0.86
	PTR2	0.927			
	PTR3	0.906			
Election Gifts	ELG1	0.875	0.892	0.734	0.822
	ELG2	0.853			
	ELG3	0.841			
Debates	DEB1	0.716	0.884	0.72	0.815
	DEB2	0.919			
	DEB3	0.896			

Intention	INT1	0.84	0.88	0.71	0.801
	INT2	0.857			
	INT3	0.831			
Attitude	ATT1	0.834	0.856	0.665	0.755
	ATT2	0.809			
	ATT3	0.803			

Table 6 Model Fit Index

Good Fitness	Criteria	Values
CMIN/DF	<5.00	1.306
CFI	>.90	0.971
IFI	>.90	0.963
TLI	>.90	0.971
RMSEA	<.08	0.044
GFI	>.90	0.92
AGFI	>.80	0.886

4.2.2 Hypothesis Testing and effects

Subsequently, the proposed hypotheses were tested after analyzing the validity of the structural model. Figure 2 presents the path analysis. The results indicate social medial political activism is positively significant to attitude ($\beta=.326^{***}$, $t=4.184$, $p<0.001$) and intention towards voting ($\beta=3.54^{***}$, $t=9.281$, $p<0.001$). Moreover, patriotism ($\beta=305^{***}$, $t=3.515$, $p<0.001$) and electoral gifts (electoral gifts $\beta=224$, $t=3.316$, $p<=0.01$) were positive and significant to attitude towards voting. These results indicate that hypothesis 1, 2,3 and 4 wateere supported. Furthermore, electoral gifts $\beta=.224^{**}$, $t=3.316$, $p<.01$), political debates ($\beta=.183^{**}$, $t=2.34$, $p<.01$) were significant and related to attitude towards voting. These results confirm hypothesis 4 and 5. Political debate was confirmed to be significant to intention ($\beta=.071^*$, $t=5.588$, $p<.05$). This confirms hypothesis 6. Finally, a significant relationship was recorded between attitude and intention to vote ($.182^{**}$, $t=3.35$, $p<.01$). In a narrower shell, the results support the proposed hypotheses in figure 1. Table 7 presents the path analysis results. The study conducted a test of indirect specific effects using the bootstrapping method at 95% confidence interval- composed of the lower and upper-level confidence interval. The results from Hayes Process (bootstrapping method) suggest that attitude mediates between the four latent variables (SM political activism, political debates, patriotism, and electoral gifts) and intention. The reverse effects were also significant. These results taken together suggests that an increase in voters' perception of patriotism, social media political activism, political debates, and electoral gifts will significantly impact on attitude-thereby finally reinforcing an inclination to form positive voting intention behavior.

In summary, the contribution of the independent variables will determine whether or not attitudes towards voting will be enhanced. The intention will be determined by their total incremental contribution. **Table 8** displays the outcomes of the Hayes Process approach.

Figure 2. Results of Structural Model. **Note:** * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 7 Path Analysis of Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path	Coefficient	T value	Interpretation
H1	SMP→INT	.354***	9.281	Supported
H2	SMP→ATT	.326***	4.814	Supported
H3	PATT→ATT	.305***	3.515	Supported
H4	ELE→ATT	.224**	3.316	Supported
H5	PDE→ATT	.183**	2.324	Supported
H6	PDE→INT	.071*	5.588	Supported
H7	ATT→INT	.182**	3.35	Supported
Control Variables				
	Gender	.261***	4.266	Significant
	Age	.068**	3.267	Significant
	Occupation	.042	1.08	Insignificant
	Education	.256***	4.278	Significant
	Construct	R²		
	ATT	0.196		
	INT	0.456		

5 Discussion

Basically, this study proposed seven hypotheses to investigate voters' behavior in Africa's oldest democratic. Considering that election is the basis of every democratic country, it is critical to investigate voters' behavior to ensure continuity of democracy. Data was gathered using a questionnaire. The SEM method was used to

analyze the data. Our research yields intriguing yet significant findings for the management and decision-making of public organizations (i.e., political parties).

Table 8 Indirect Specific Effects

Path	Estimate	95% confidence interval		Result
		Lower level	Upper level	
SMP → ATT → INT	.0621	.0081	.1310	Supported
PAT → ATT → INT	.0457	.0025	.0979	Supported
DEB → ATT → INT	.0492	.0040	.1077	Supported
ELG → ATT → INT	.1471	.0629	.2565	Supported

Firstly, the results from data analysis revealed a significant relationship between social media political activism and voters' intention to vote. Similarly, a significant relationship between social media political activism and voters' attitudes towards voting was affirmed. The salience of social media political activism on voters' attitudes and voting intention amplifies the harnessable potentials of social media political activism. This finding is consistent with [Frimpong et al. \(2020\)](#), who found that social media political activism affect voting behavior of Ghanaians. Similarly, we can conclude that political activism through social media also influences voters' attitudes and intentions in Botswana. Our results side with the optimist view that SM has a catalytic effect towards encouraging more people to participate in politics, and the normalizer view, that SM provides strong political reinforcement towards enhancing the interest of people who are already interested in politics ([Casteltrione, 2015](#)).

Additionally, the results from the study corroborated the significant relationship between electoral gifts and attitude towards voting. This implies that voters in Botswana are enticed through gifts to vote. However, [Stokes \(2007\)](#) argued that usage of electoral gifts to lure voters undermines the quality of democracy and slows economic development. In light of this argument, we also hold that the presence of electoral gifts to influence voters' attitudes towards voting is detrimental to democracy. We argue on the basis that, electoral gifts create a system of dependency, poverty, and less commitment to the improvement of quality of life. In addition to that electoral gifts undermines the prudence of democracy on the basis it vitiates democracy by undermining the equality of the ballot, allowing some voters to use their votes to communicate policy preferences while others use their votes only as an exchange for minor side payments. The fact that we discerned the significant presence of electoral gifts and attitude nexus in Botswana, [Stokes \(2007\)](#)'s argument on the detrimental impacts of electoral gits on voting behavior is likely to prevail in the context of Botswana. We highly recommend that political parties should desist from this act to preserve democracy.

As prior echoed by [Arkorful & Lugu \(2021\)](#), the study also confirmed the significant impact of political debates on attitude and intention. This accentuates the salience of debates in broader democratic engagements such as

voting in Sub-Saharan Africa. Given that debates allow political parties and candidates to express their policies and programs, attract voters, foster dialogue, and reduce tensions that characterize elections and political campaigns while strengthening and consolidating democratic governance, parties must demonstrate adherence to these principles. Moreover, the study confirms a significant relationship between patriotism and attitude. This implies that citizens of Botswana still express patriotism through voting. This is interesting because patriotism has declined in most of the African countries due to civil unrest and election rigging.

Furthermore, voters' voting intentions were found to have a significant positive relationship with their attitude toward voting. In light of this result, it is important to emphasize that the determination of attitude, which is critical to predicting intention behavior, is informed by the additive and incremental contribution of extraneous factors (i.e., political debates, social media political activism, and patriotism). This is supported by an increase in attitude explained variance from 0.196 to 0.456 ($R^2=0.26$), a result presupposing that an increase in attitude (determined by an increase in any of the extraneous variables) will consequently trigger an increase in intention. Further, our study examined the relationship between control variables and voters' voting intention behavior. On this score, gender ($\beta=.261^{***}$, $t=4.266$, $p<.001$), age ($\beta=.068^{**}$, $t=3.267$, $p<.01$), and education ($\beta=.256^{***}$, $t=4.278$, $p<.001$) were statistically significant. However, occupation ($\beta=.042$, $t=1.08$) was insignificant. A summary of our study's findings demonstrates that political debates, electoral gifts social media political activism, and patriotism all play a significant role in shaping voters' voting intention behavior.

6 Conclusion, Limitation and Future Research Avenues

In summary, the study intends to contribute to a set of practical suggestions to assist relevant governance bodies such as political parties in increasing their efficiency and effectiveness in electoral decision-making and resource allocation. The study found that voters' behavior is influenced by sense of patriotism, electoral gifts, social media political activists, and political debates. As a result, it is vital for political parties to capitalize on some of these features in order to effectively attract voters. Given the critical role political parties play in establishing and sustaining democratic governance by facilitating peaceful leadership transitions through elections, it is critical to ascertain the motivations of voters, who are a cornerstone of the democratic governance process. Thus, this study conducted an empirical investigation and confirmed the significance of political debates, electoral gifts, political activism on social media, and patriotism. With reference to these outcomes, it is critical for political leaders to exercise caution when using electoral gifts to attract voters to safeguard the quality of democracy. Additionally, it becomes critical that a portion of political parties' proactive and innovative efforts aimed at identifying and exploiting opportunities for appealing electoral outcomes are geared toward harvesting electoral yields from debates and political activism on social media. Despite external factors such as electoral gifts and debates, a sense of patriotism encourages voters to participate in elections when all other factors are held constant. As a result, political parties must acknowledge that, in addition to the gifts they provide, voters are occasionally swayed by a sense of patriotism toward their country.

Notwithstanding the contributions offered by this study, our study has limitations that need to be addressed. Our study used cross-sectional data; however, time-series data should be used in the future to analyze voters' behavior throughout various time periods to improve the study's outcomes. We also advise researchers interested in this topic to look into other factors that may influence voter behavior, such as institutional trust. Furthermore, the study's generalizability and replication in other contexts may be limited. As a result, we recommend that future studies take socio-cultural factors into account when attempting to test our study model in different geographical contexts.

References

- Adams S & Agomor KS (2015) Democratic politics and voting behavior in Ghana. *International Area Studies Review* 18(4): 365-381.
- Ajzen I & Fishbein M (1975) A Bayesian analysis of attribution processes. *Psychological bulletin* 82(2): 261.
- Ajzen I & Fishbein M (1977) Attitude-behavior relations: A theoretical analysis and review of empirical research. *Psychological bulletin* 84(5): 888.
- Anderson CJ (2007) The interaction of structures and voter behavior. *The oxford handbook of political behavior*.
- Anderson JC & Gerbing DW (1988) Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological bulletin* 103(3): 411.
- Arkorful VE, Hammond A, Lugu BK, et al. (2020) Investigating the intention to use technology among medical students: An application of an extended model of the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Public Affairs*. e2460.
- Arkorful VE & Lugu BK (2021) Voters' behavior: Probing the salience of Manifestoes, Debates, Ideology and Celebrity Endorsement. *Public Organization Review*. 1-20.
- Bates RH (1974) Ethnic competition and modernization in contemporary Africa. *Comparative political studies* 6(4): 457-484.
- Bidwell K, Casey K & Glennerster R (2016) Debates: Voting and expenditure responses to political communication. *Unpublished paper*.
- Bimber B (1998) The Internet and political transformation: Populism, community, and accelerated pluralism. *Polity* 31(1): 133-160.
- Bratton M & Kimenyi MS (2008) Voting in Kenya: Putting ethnicity in perspective. *Journal of Eastern African Studies* 2(2): 272-289.
- Brierley S, Kramon E & Ofori GK (2020) The moderating effect of debates on political attitudes. *American Journal of Political Science* 64(1): 19-37.
- Casteltrione I (2015) The Internet, social networking Web sites and political participation research: Assumptions and contradictory evidence. *First Monday*.
- Castro CR & Beltrán U (2020) Who receives electoral gifts? It depends on question wording: experimental evidence from Mexico. *Political Behavior*. 1-29.
- Datta K (1991) *Democracy and Elections in Botswana: With Some Reference to General Literature on Democracy and Elections in Africa: Bibliography*. Centre d'étude d'Afrique noire, Institut d'études politiques de Bordeaux.
- Dewa D (2009) Factors affecting voting behavior and voting patterns in Zimbabwe's 2008 harmonized elections. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations* 3(11): 490-496.
- Downs A (1957) An economic theory of political action in a democracy. *Journal of political economy* 65(2): 135-150.
- Frimpong ANK, Li P, Nyame G, et al. (2020) The Impact of Social Media Political Activists on Voting Patterns. *Political Behavior*. 1-54.
- Guardado J & Wantchekon L (2014) Do electoral handouts affect voting behavior. Reportno. Report Number|, Date. Place Published|: Institution|.

- Guardado J & Wantchekon L (2017) Do electoral handouts affect voting behaviour? Afro Barometer. *Working Paper No. 171*.
- Hair J, Anderson R, Babin B, et al. (2010) *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*: Pearson Upper Saddle River. NJ.
- Hair JF, Ringle CM & Sarstedt M (2013) Partial least squares structural equation modeling: Rigorous applications, better results and higher acceptance. *Long range planning* 46(1-2): 1-12.
- Harder J & Krosnick JA (2008) Why do people vote? A psychological analysis of the causes of voter turnout. *Journal of Social Issues* 64(3): 525-549.
- Henseler J, Ringle CM & Sarstedt M (2015) A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the academy of marketing science* 43(1): 115-135.
- Horowitz DL (1985) *Ethnic groups in conflict*. Berkeley, CA: Univ. of California press.
- Kaiser HF (1974) An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika* 39(1): 31-36.
- Kimenyi MS & Romero RG (2008) Identity, grievances, and economic determinants of voting in the 2007 Kenyan elections.
- Kosterman R & Feshbach S (1989) Toward a measure of patriotic and nationalistic attitudes. *Political psychology*. 257-274.
- Lewis T (2017) Fit Statistics commonly reported for CFA and SEM. *Cornell Statistics Department* 8: 0-1.
- Masilo B & Seabo B (2015) Facebook: revolutionising electoral campaign in Botswana? *Journal of African Elections* 14(2): 110-129.
- Milotova K (2021) Patriotism and Political Participation in the Visegrad Group countries. Reportno. Report Number|, Date. Place Published|: Institution|.
- Milotová K (2009) of Thesis: Patriotism and Political Participation in the. *Age* 18(29): 30-49.
- Mohanachandran DK & Govindarajo NS (2020) Theory of Reasoned Action and Citizen's Voting Behaviour. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities* 28(1).
- Nichter S (2008) Vote buying or turnout buying? Machine politics and the secret ballot. *American political science review* 102(1): 19-31.
- Richey S (2011) Civic engagement and patriotism. *Social Science Quarterly* 92(4): 1044-1056.
- Schatz RT, Staub E & Lavine H (1999) On the varieties of national attachment: Blind versus constructive patriotism. *Political psychology* 20(1): 151-174.
- Steinberg A (2015) Exploring Web 2.0 political engagement: Is new technology reducing the biases of political participation? *Electoral Studies* 39: 102-116.
- Stokes SC (2007) *The Oxford handbook of political science*.
- Tang G & Lee FL (2013) Facebook use and political participation: The impact of exposure to shared political information, connections with public political actors, and network structural heterogeneity. *Social science computer review* 31(6): 763-773.
- Theiss-Morse E, Fried A, Sullivan JL, et al. (1991) Mixing methods: A multistage strategy for studying patriotism and citizen participation. *Political Analysis* 3: 89-121.
- Young C (2002) *Ethnicity and politics in Africa*. Boston University, African Studies Center.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.